

Leachates from Electronic Waste Alter Biochemical Parameters and Cause Genotoxicity in Exposed Albino Rats (*Mus musculus*)

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Abstract

Studies have shown that exposure to electronic waste leachate from landfills, industrial processes, or agriculture can pose health risks to humans and animals. However, the exact nature of the health problems has not been established. This study evaluated the physicochemical parameters and effects of leachate from e-waste collected from Alaba International Market, Lagos on Swiss albino mice. Forty-two rats of both sexes were distributed equally into 7 groups. The control rats in group 1 were fed distilled water while the test rats in groups 2-7 were fed 0.5ml 100%, 50%, 25%, 10%, 5%, and 1% v/v of the leachate, respectively. The administration was monitored for 16 days, during which clinical observations and body weight measurement were also carried out. Thereafter, the rats were euthanized and their liver, kidney and sperm functions were determined. The genotoxicity of the leachate was also evaluated. Physicochemical analysis showed that pH, turbidity, conductivity, TSS, etc.) exceeded the standards set by the World health organization (WHO) and the Nigeria standard for water quality (NSDWQ). The results also revealed elevated liver enzymes (AST, ALT) and kidney damage (CREA); reduced sperm count and motility; increased sperm aberrations; and DNA damage in liver cells, including single-strand breaks and double-strand breaks in mice exposed to e-waste leachate. The study concludes that e-waste leachate is cytotoxic and genotoxic, posing potential health risks to humans and animals. Minimizing human exposure, proper management and disposal of e-waste are crucial to prevent adverse health effects and mitigate its toxicity on human health and the environment.

Keywords: Antimalarial, Bio active compounds, Efficacy, Metabolites, *Plasmodium berghei*

1.0 Introduction

The menace of pollution has become a significant threat to the environment and human health, largely due to rapid industrialization and technological advancements. The unprecedented growth of industries and technology has led to an increase in environmental pollution, posing severe risks to ecosystems and human well-being [1,2]. One of the

devastating consequences of technological progress is the generation of electronic waste (e-waste), which has become a major environmental concern globally [3]. E-waste is a complex mixture of toxic substances, including heavy metals, flame retardants, and other hazardous chemicals [4]. These substances can contaminate soil, water, and air, posing serious health risks to humans and wildlife [5]. Genotoxins, such as lead, cadmium, and

chromium, are particularly concerning, as they can cause genetic damage and mutations [6]. The possible effects of e-waste exposure include cancer, reproductive problems, and neurological damage ([7]. However, the nature and extent of these effects are not yet fully understood, and there are conflicting results in the literature [8]. For instance, some studies have reported significant genotoxic effects of e-waste exposure, while others have found no such effects [9,10].

To address this research gap, this study focused on the effects of leachates from e-waste on genetic material. Leachates are liquids that seep through e-waste and can contaminate soil and water. The Comet Assay is an appropriate technique for this research due to its sensitivity, versatility, and ability to detect DNA damage at the individual cell level [11]. The Comet Assay has been widely used to assess genotoxicity in various environmental and occupational exposure studies [12]. The study was design to investigate the genotoxic effects of leachates from e-waste using the Comet Assay; also to determine the levels of genotoxins in e-waste leachates and their potential impact on human health as well as contribute to the understanding of the environmental and health risks associated with e-waste exposure. By achieving these objectives, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the effects of e-waste leachates on genetic material and contribute to the development of strategies for mitigating the environmental and health impacts of e-waste.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Description of Study Site

Electronic wastes were collected from Alaba International Market in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State, South-western Nigeria located at located at 6°23'N and 2°42'E latitude and longitude, respectively. The market has both legal and illicit locations for disposing of various kinds of broken, abandoned, and irreparable electronics. Alaba market has been described previously [13].

2.2 Sample Collection and Leachate Formulation

Samples including soil granules, trash, and electronic garbage were obtained from different locations at the market's illicit disposal site. Samples were taken from the south, north, east and west, and middle of the dumpsite, pooled together, of which 10

kg were weighed. The debris was removed therein after 10 kg of soil particles were weighed and dissolved for 24 hours in 10 litres of distilled water. This gave the resultant stock of electronic waste solution. From this, 500ml of simulated leachate in different concentrations, was created and placed in clean plastic bottles). The concentrations used were 100%, 50%, 25%, 10%, 5%, and 1% (v/v, simulant/distilled water).

2.3 Physicochemical analysis of the leachate

A number of parameters like turbidity, PH, conductivity, total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS) and heavy metals such as copper, zinc, manganese, iron, chloride, nitrate, sulphate, cadmium, nickel and chromium were analyzed for each leachate concentration following the method of [14], then compared the results with the standard set by World health organization (WHO) and local standards such as Nigeria standard for water quality (NSDWQ).

2.4 Animal and experimental design

All animal experiments were conducted in accordance with standard guidelines as set by University of Lagos Research and Ethic Committee on use of animals for experimental toxicology study. Male and female Swiss Albino mice (*Mus musculus*; 8 – 10 weeks old, 17 – 26 kg) were obtained. They were acclimatized for 7 days in well-ventilated plastic cages in the animal house of the Cell Biology and Genetics Department, University of Lagos, Nigeria. The experiment lasted for 14 days and the mice were fed with commercial pellets obtained from Agege Abattoir, Lagos and clean water. The mice were separated based on gender into 7 groups with 3 mice per group. The control group (group 1) was treated with distilled water only, while the remaining groups were treated daily with 0.5ml of electronic waste leachate (1%, 5%, 10%, 25%, 50% and 100%) respectively. They were housed in cages (three in each) at controlled room temperature of 25 ± 2 °C and a constant light-dark schedule (12 hours' light and dark cycle).

2.5 Clinical observations and body weight measurement

Each mouse in each of the treatment group was observed daily (before and after treatment) for weight change, and signs of clinical toxicity in the

appearances of the skin and fur, eyes, behavioural pattern, morbidity and mortality.

2.6 Clinical pathology

The blood samples were collected from the mice through retro- orbital sinus punctuation using a haematocrit capillary tube which was transferred into plain bottles and EDTA bottles. Clear Sera was prepared from the blood samples. It was used in the determination of various biochemical renal parameters with the aid of Randox diagnostics kits. The activities of creatinine (CREA), bilirubin (BILB) and urea (UREA) were observed in both males and females. The liver function tests analysed include alanine transaminase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), glutamine, albumin (ALB), total protein (TP) concentration, cholesterol (CHOL), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), low-density lipoprotein (LML), triglyceride (TG), and alpha-lipoic acid (ALPH/L) tests. Semen was collected from the male mice by rupturing the epididymis of the mice. Briefly, the caudal epididymis was lacerated with scissors after being carefully separated from the testis as described by Boersma *et al.*(2015) [15].

2.7 Comet Assay

The comet assay was performed in triplicate using the protocol designed for single cell gel electrophoresis prepared by Dhawan *et al.*, (2009) [16], with some modifications. 1% and 0.5% of LMPA was prepared respectively by dissolving 500mg of LMPA powder in 50ml PBS and 250mg LMPA powder in 50ml PBS. 1% NMA was prepared by dissolving 500mg in 50ml of sterilized water. The samples were heated until near boiling and agarose dissolved. For LMPA, 5ml samples were aliquoted and stored until when in use. The slides were dipped in methanol and passed over a blue flame to remove the machine oil and dust. While the NMA agarose was hot, one-third of the frosted area of the slides were dipped gently and removed. The under-side of the slides were wiped with a paper towel to remove the NMA and placed on a tray to dry and stored at room temperature before use.

2.8 Solid Organ or Tissue Treatment

A small piece of the organ: liver was placed in 1 ml of cold HBSS and minced into fine pieces. One ml of mincing solution, HBSS was added again and

aspirated using a micropipette. Afterwards, 5ul of the cell suspension was transferred to a vial. 75ul of LMPA was added to the solution and mixed. The solution was kept in a heat-block at 40 °C. Then, the mixture was placed on NMA pre-coated slides and covered with coverslips [17].

2.9 Electrophoresis of Microgel Slides

The slides were gently removed from the lysis solution after 8hrs of being stored at -4 °C. The slides were placed side by side on the horizontal gel box. The horizontal gel box was filled with electrophoresis buffer (alkaline buffer EDTA, NaCl, Tris, Triton X-100, DMSO) till it covered the slides completely. The slides were left in the alkaline buffer for 20 minutes to unwind the DNA. The power pack of the electric chamber was turned on to 24 volts (constant), adjusted to 300 milliamperes. The electrophoresis chamber was covered with a paper towel and slides were electrophoresed for 30 minutes based on the sample tissue (liver). After the intended time has elapsed, the slides were gently removed from the buffer and placed on a dry tray [18].

2.10 Neutralization, Staining, Scoring and Visualization of Slides using Fluorescence Microscopy

The slides were coated with neutralization buffer using a Pasteur pipette and allowed to sit in the solution for 5 minutes. The slides were drained and protocol repeated again for two consecutive times. The slides were dehydrated in 100% cold methanol for 20 minutes. The slides were air dried and stored in a dry area. The slides were stained with geimsa for 20 minutes at room temperature and covered with a fresh cover-slip. Excess stain on the edges and back of the slides were blotted with a paper towel in order to enable viewing. The slides were stained with 50ul Geimsa stain and kept for 5 minutes; the slides were examined under a fluorescence inverted microscope. The genotoxic and cytotoxic effect was evaluated by quantification on the comet 5 image analysis linked to AMSCOPE camera (model number: MD35) to assess the quantitative and qualitative extent of DNA damage in the cells. In total, 84 slides were analysed and the frequencies of the DNA damage were scored using imagej_v1.3.1, derived excel sheets were cleaned [17].

2.11 Statistical Analysis

Data generated for liver, kidney and semen tests were analysed using IBM SPSS v26 (IBM Corp., USA). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to access the level of significance among treatment groups and differences between groups was separated using Bonferroni's test at $p < 0.05$. Data generated for comet assay were analyzed using GraphPad Prism 8. One-way ANOVA and two-way ANOVA were used to assess individual DNA damage of the liver cell, measuring the length of

DNA migration, percentage of migrated DNA and tail moment.

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 Physicochemical characteristics

The physical observation of the electronic leachates acquired all yielded results above the standard of the WHO and the NSDWQ as shown in Table 2. The physicochemical parameters of the leachate across all parameters failed to meet the WHO standard, with analysis rendering them "not within limits".

Table 2: Levels of physico-chemical parameters and heavy metals in e-waste leachate obtained from Alaba Market, Lagos

S/N	Parameters	Unit	Results	WHO (NSDWQ)	Remarks
Physical / Organoleptic Parameters					
1	Appearance		Black	Clear	Not within limits
2	pH @20 ^o c	-	6.22	6.5-8.5	Not within limits
3	Colour	TUC	Black	Colourless	Not within limits
5	Odour	-	Odour present	Odourless	Not within limits
6	Turbidity	NTU	>5	5	Not within limits
7	Conductivity	μS/cm ³	3,990.00	0.9X10 ⁻³ -1.20X 10 ³	Not within limits
8	Total Dissolved Solids	mg/L	2,394.00	500	Not within limits
9	Total Solids	mg/L	Above limits	500	Not within limits
Chemical Parameters					
11	Total Hardness (CaCO ₃)	mg/L	5,722.00	30-200	Not within limits
12	Total Alkalinity (CaCO ₃)	mg/L	238	30.5	Not within limits
13	Total Acidity (CaCO ₃)	mg/L	117	50	Not within limits
14	Calcium (CaCO ₃)	mg/L	2293.38	50	Not within limits
15	Magnesium (CaCO ₃)	mg/L	833.16	50	Not within limits
16	Chloride (Cl ⁻)	mg/L	59,931.77	200-600	Not within limits
17	Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	mg/L	75.54	5-30	Not within limits
18	Sulphate	mg/L	121.74	100	Not within limits
19	Phosphate	mg/L	4.046	0.03	Not within limits
21	Copper	mg/L	248.7	0.005-1.50	Not within limits
22	Manganese	mg/L	205	0.005-0.5	Not within limits
23	Iron	mg/L	311.32	0.1-1.0	Not within limits
24	Zinc	mg/L	2085.93	5.00 -15.00	Not within limits
25	Lead	mg/L	218.23	0.01	Not within limits
26	Cadmium	mg/L	5.72	0.003	Not within limits
27	Nickel	mg/L	521.54	0.02	Not within limits
28	Chromium	mg/L	57.42	0.05	Not within limits

3.2 Clinical Signs of Toxicity and Mortality

During the first week of exposure, 4 male mice died (1 from each concentration) and the survivors showed clinical signs of toxicity such as hair loss, tail decay, aggressiveness and colour change of the skin within the first 7 days of the experiment (Figure

1a-d). Hair loss was observed in mice exposed to 5%, 10%, 25% and 100% of the leachates in the first five days of the experiment. Aggressiveness was observed in both genders of mice (one male treated with 50% leachate and one female treated with 1% leachate). After 11 days, males treated with 100% leachates showed decayed fur and skin colour

changes. Male mice treated with 50% of leachate experienced swollen or enlarged stomach. Additionally, male mice treated with 25% leachate concentration had lumps in the tails. There was further loss of fur and shortening of tails among males exposed to 25% concentration on day 12. Also, males exposed to 50% and 10% had an

a: Initial decay of tail

enlarged scrotum size while male exposed to 100% concentration experienced loss of fur, lump in the tail, swollen scrotum, lump in the body and loss of fur in the tail region. On the 14th day, male mice exposed to 50%, 25%, 10% and 1% leachate concentration showed enlarged scrotum.

b: Blisters on the tail

c: Shortening of the tail

d: Enlarged Scrotum

Figure 1: Rats exposed to e-waste leachate showing clinical toxicities

3.3 Biochemical indicator of hepatic and renal functions

Table 3 (a-b) and figure 2 (a-f) show the results of serum biochemical tests. There was a concentration-dependent significant difference in the activities of serum AST ($p < 0.01$), ALT ($p < 0.01$), T.P ($p < 0.05$), LML ($p < 0.05$), CHOL ($p < 0.05$) and ALPH/L ($p < 0.01$) enzymes in leachate exposed to male mice's liver compared to the negative control. The AST levels were determined in male mice

treated with different concentrations of leachates. The treatment effects of control, 1%, 5% and 10% concentration had no significant difference in AST levels of mice among themselves. Likewise, the treatment effects of 5% and 25% concentrations on AST levels in male mice were not significantly different from one another. However, the effect of 25% was significantly different from the treatment with control, 1%, and 10% leachate concentrations. The treatment effect of 100% leachate concentration on AST levels differed from the effects of control,

1%, 5%, 10% and 25%. However, the treatment effect of 50% leachate concentration was not statistically different from 100% on AST levels in the mice. The treatment effect of 100% leachate concentration on AST levels was significantly higher than all treatments except 50% leachate concentration. However, the treatment effect of 25% leachate concentration was not significantly different from 50% leachate concentration on AST levels in the mice. The treatment effects of control, 1%, 5% and 100% leachates concentrations on ALT levels were not significantly different from one another. However, ALT levels in mice treated with 10% leachate concentration was significantly lower compared to the remaining treatment groups. Mice treated with 50% leachate concentration had a significantly higher ALT levels than all other treatment groups. Furthermore, mice treated with 25% leachate concentration had the second highest ALT levels and it was found significantly different from all other treatment groups. The T.P levels of mice was assessed to determine the effect of leachate concentrations. Male mice treated with 10% leachate concentration had the lowest T.P values. Meanwhile, mice in the treatment groups exposed to 1%, 5%, 25% and 100% leachate concentrations had TP levels that were not significantly different from one another. The effects of leachate concentrations in mice exposed to 50% and those in the control group had no significant differences observed in their TP levels. Male albino mice exposed to 5% leachate concentration had a significant higher LML value compared to all other treatment groups. The remaining treatment concentrations had similar effects on LML levels in male albino mice.

There is concentration-dependent statistical difference in the activities of serum AST ($p < 0.05$), ALT ($p < 0.01$), LML ($p < 0.01$), T.G ($p < 0.01$) and ALPH/L ($p < 0.05$) enzymes in leachate exposed female mice compared to the negative control. The AST levels observed in female albino mice showed no significant difference in the exposure of the female to control, 1%, 5%, 10%, and 25% leachate concentration. However, ALT levels observed in females exposed to 25% and 50% leachate concentration showed no significant difference between them. Furthermore, AST level in female mice exposed to 100% leachate concentration was statistically higher compared to other treatments. ALT levels were determined after the treatment of leachate concentrations on female albino mice. Result shows that ALT levels were higher in female mice treated with 1% leachate concentration

compared to other treatment groups. Although, ALT levels observed in female mice treated with 1% and 100% leachate concentration had no statistical difference. The treatment effects of control, 5%, 10% and 25% leachate concentrations on ALT levels in female mice were not significantly different from one another. However, the treatment effect of 25% leachate concentration on ALT levels of the female mice was statistically lower than those exposed to 50% leachate concentration. Lowest ALT levels were observed in mice exposed to 25% leachate concentration. Also, the treatment effect of 50% leachate concentrations on ALT levels was not statistically different from ALT levels in female mice exposed to 100% leachate concentration. The treatment effect of 100% leachate concentration recorded the statistically lowest LML levels in female mice compared to other treatment groups. The highest LML levels was observed in female mice treated with 50% leachate concentration. Although, LML levels observed in female mice treated with 0%, 10% and 50% leachate concentrations had similar effects. In female mice treated with control and 5% leachates concentrations, LML levels were statistically similar. Also, there was no significant difference observed in LML levels between female mice treated with 1% and 5% concentrations. The treatment effect of 100% concentration on LML levels was significantly lower compared to the treatment groups. Female mice treated with 100% concentration had the highest ALPH/L levels. The remaining concentrations had similar effects on ALPH/L levels in female mice. T.G levels were at the highest in female treated with 25% concentration. The treatment effects of control, 1%, 5% and 100% concentrations had similar statistical TG levels. Similarly, female mice treated with 1%, 5% and 50% had statistically similar TG levels. Lowest TG level was observed in female mice treated with 0% concentration. The treatment of female mice with 10% and 50% leachate concentrations respectively had similar effect on TG levels in the treated female mice.

There was a concentration dependent statistically significant difference in the activities of serum creatinine (CREA) ($F = 11.00$, $P < 0.01$) and urea ($F = 6.90$, $P < 0.05$) enzymes in leachate exposed female mice's kidney compared to the negative control. However, there was no statistical significance between bilirubin (BILB) and the negative control ($F = 2.89$, $P > 0.05$) (Figure 2a). In creatinine (CREA) treatment among females, the

treatment effects of control, 1%, 5%, 10%, 25%, and 100% had no significant difference. Only treatment effect of 50% differed from the rest. It was significantly higher in concentration value (Figure 2b). The same effect similarity was observed in treatment on UREA, there was no statistically significant difference between control, 1%, 5%, 10%, 25% and 100%. Like CREA, 50% was significantly higher than the rest of the treatment administered (Figure 2c). Similarly, the treatment of leachate concentration was also tested in the kidney of the male albino mice with the targeted enzymes being bilirubin (BIL), creatinine (CREA) and Urea. There was a concentration dependent statistical difference in the activities of serum BIL ($F = 4.82$, $P < 0.05$) (Figure 4) and CREA ($F = 19.60$, $P < 0.01$) (Figure 5) enzymes in leachate exposed female mice's kidney compared to the negative control. However, there was no statistical significance between BILB and the negative control ($F = 1.59$, $P > 0.05$) (Figure 2d). The treatment effects of control, 1%, 5%, 10%, 50% and 100% were not statistically significantly different on BIL. Also, the treatments of control, 5%, 10%, 25%, 50% and 100% had similar effects on BIL. However, the treatment effects of 1% and 25% were statistically different, with 25% being slightly higher (Figure 2e). The treatment effect of 10% had the lowest concentration value on CREA and it was significantly different from other treatment concentrations ($p < 0.01$). Another treatment effect that significantly different from other treatment effects was 1%, although it slightly higher than 10%. The remaining treatments control, 5%, 25%, 50% and 100% all had the same effect. There was no significant difference among the treatment effects on UREA (Figure 2f).

3.4 Levels of Biochemical of Parameters of the Rats across Sexes

The result of independent t-test used to compare animal gender responses to the treatment was shown Table 4. The different treatment with leachate concentrations on male and female mice had similar effects between the two genders in their respective AST levels. ALT levels were different in animals treated with 1%, 50%, and 100% leachate concentration ($P < 0.05$). GLU levels observed in animals treated with leachate concentrations were statistically similar in the different treatment groups respectively. Similarly, T.P levels observed in the male mice and female mice treated with leachate concentrations were statistically similar in the different treatment groups respectively. Likewise, HDL levels were not significantly different between the two genders treated to different leachate concentrations respectively. Male mice LML levels were higher than females treated with 5%, 25% and 100% e-waste leachate ($P < 0.05$). However, in mice treated with 10%, females had higher LML levels ($P < 0.01$). CHOL levels in males treated with 10% concentration of leachate was significantly lower than the level observed in female mice treated with same concentration of leachates ($P < 0.05$). TG levels showed higher levels in females treated with 25% leachate concentration compared to males treated with 25% leachate concentration ($p < 0.01$). Lastly, ALPH/L levels observed in the male mice and female mice treated with leachate concentrations were statistically similar in the different treatment groups respectively. The response of the males and females to treatment effects on BIL had no significance differences across all treatment concentration. Creatinine levels were higher in females than males treated with 10% ($P < 0.01$) and 50% ($P < 0.05$) leachate concentration respectively. Urea levels were similar between the two genders at every treatment concentration.

Table 3a: Levels of hepatic function parameters in male mice treated with e-waste leachate

Treatment	AST H/L	ALT NL U/L	GLU MMOL	ALB b/l	T.P g/l	HDL Mmol/l	LML Mmol/l	CHOL Mmol/l	T.G Mmol/l	ALPH/L u/l
Control	152.10 ± 11.74 ^a	31.70 ± 2.83 ^b	5.20 ± 0.71	41.10 ± 2.55	73.40 ± 5.66 ^{cd}	1.48 ± 0.11	1.88 ± 0.05 ^a	2.44 ± 0.25	1.26 ± 0.13	101.80 ± 16.40
1%	148.10 ± 7.21 ^a	32.00 ± 3.54 ^b	5.80 ± 0.57	24.00 ± 3.54	58.60 ± 4.24 ^b	1.00 ± 0.30	1.55 ± 0.06 ^a	2.21 ± 0.08	1.48 ± 0.14	74.60 ± 3.54
5%	187.40 ± 7.07 ^{ab}	37.50 ± 1.41 ^b	4.30 ± 0.42	35.40 ± 35.98	66.90 ± 2.83 ^{bc}	1.67 ± 0.13	2.48 ± 0.33 ^b	3.13 ± 0.40	1.44 ± 0.20	65.70 ± 4.24
10%	184.40 ± 13.01 ^a	21.50 ± 4.53 ^a	4.70 ± 0.57	23.10 ± 2.55	48.80 ± 2.55 ^a	1.26 ± 0.37	1.46 ± 0.17 ^a	1.77 ± 0.07	1.13 ± 0.49	68.40 ± 5.66
25%	223.10 ± 12.02 ^{bc}	53.10 ± 6.36 ^c	5.00 ± 0.42	25.40 ± 8.20	63.70 ± 0.71 ^{bc}	0.85 ± 0.06	1.61 ± 0.17 ^a	2.19 ± 0.13	1.28 ± 0.18	61.70 ± 4.24
50%	243.00 ± 18.81 ^{cd}	79.10 ± 3.68 ^d	4.80 ± 0.57	35.60 ± 1.56	70.10 ± 3.11 ^d	1.43 ± 0.13	1.81 ± 0.16 ^a	2.66 ± 0.25	1.34 ± 0.18	118.80 ± 4.24
100%	267.00 ± 28.57 ^d	41.80 ± 4.24 ^b	5.60 ± 0.42	30.00 ± 6.65	62.90 ± 5.66 ^{bc}	1.26 ± 0.21	1.89 ± 0.08 ^a	2.25 ± 0.25	0.78 ± 0.12	136.00 ± 8.49
F-stat	16.60**	43.53**	1.91ns	1.69ns	8.61*	3.46ns	8.03*	6.75*	200ns	27.49**

*, ** Significant at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$; ns: not significant; values represent mean \pm std (n = 2) followed by different alphabets are significantly different at $P < 0.05$; AST – Aspartate aminotransferase, ALT – Alanine transaminase, GLU – Glutamine, ALB – Albumin, T.P – Total protein, HDL – High Density Lipoprotein, LML – Low Density Lipoprotein, CHOL – Cholesterol, T.G – Triglycerides, ALPH/A – Alpha-Lipoic Acid

Table 3b: Levels of hepatic function parameters in female mice treated with e-waste leachate

Treatment	AST H/L	ALT NL U/L	GLU MMOL	ALB b/l	T.P g/l	HDL Mmol/l	LML Mmol/l	CHOL Mmol/l	T.G Mmol/l	ALPH/L u/l
Control	169.30 ± 3.11 ^a	40.00 ± 4.10 ^{ab}	5.30 ± 0.42	19.40 ± 2.69 ^a	62.90 ± 6.51	1.20 ± 0.14	2.07 ± 0.16 ^{de}	2.43 ± 0.08	0.80 ± 0.21 ^a	97.20 ± 8.77 ^a
1%	146.40 ± 7.35 ^a	90.30 ± 11.17 ^d	4.60 ± 0.28	20.70 ± 2.69 ^a	60.00 ± 3.96	1.15 ± 1.15	1.49 ± 0.18 ^c	2.06 ± 0.28	1.27 ± 0.11 ^{ab}	75.70 ± 0.00 ^a
5%	158.10 ± 55.30 ^a	38.50 ± 20.65 ^{ab}	5.30 ± 0.28	33.30 ± 6.08 ^b	65.10 ± 3.82	1.19 ± 1.19	1.68 ± 0.23 ^{cd}	2.15 ± 0.23	1.05 ± 0.37 ^{ab}	60.90 ± 5.37 ^a
10%	177.00 ± 21.78 ^a	42.90 ± 6.22 ^{ab}	4.70 ± 0.99	34.10 ± 3.82 ^b	70.09 ± 6.38	1.43 ± 1.43	2.16 ± 0.18 ^e	2.93 ± 0.23	1.70 ± 0.33 ^c	61.70 ± 9.62 ^a
25%	200.20 ± 21.92 ^{ab}	29.95 ± 6.01 ^a	4.60 ± 0.42	26.00 ± 7.35 ^{ab}	58.80 ± 6.93	1.45 ± 1.45	1.07 ± 0.17 ^b	3.20 ± 1.02	3.70 ± 0.24 ^d	64.20 ± 7.78 ^a
50%	256.85 ± 9.26 ^b	55.20 ± 4.24 ^{bc}	4.20 ± 0.14	28.25 ± 5.59 ^{ab}	70.40 ± 4.10	1.36 ± 1.36	2.23 ± 0.13 ^e	2.92 ± 0.08	1.52 ± 0.16 ^{bc}	93.00 ± 32.95 ^a
100%	280.60 ± 9.62 ^c	74.40 ± 3.39 ^{cd}	5.00 ± 0.28	31.30 ± 2.97 ^{ab}	64.20 ± 3.25	1.44 ± 1.44	0.54 ± 0.10 ^a	2.38 ± 0.06	0.89 ± 0.04 ^a	139.20 ± 11.46 ^b
F-stat	8.67*	9.95**	1.44ns	3.01ns	1.51ns	1.27ns	27.77**	2.15ns	36.42**	7.58*

*, ** Significant at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$; ns: not significant; values represent mean \pm std (n = 2) followed by different alphabets are significantly different at $P < 0.05$; AST – Aspartate aminotransferase, ALT – Alanine transaminase, GLU – Glutamine, ALB – Albumin, T.P – Total protein, HDL – High Density Lipoprotein, LML – Low Density Lipoprotein, CHOL – Cholesterol, T.G – Triglycerides, ALPH/A – Alpha-Lipoic Acid

Figure 2a-c: Levels of renal function parameters in female mice treated with e-waste leachate

Figure 2d-f: Levels of renal function parameters in male mice treated with e-waste leachate

Table 4: Biochemical comparative responses of the rats to treatment by genders

Parameters	Treatment	Male	Female	t
AST H/L	Control	152.10 ±11.74	169.30±3.11	0.83ns
	1%	148.10±7.21	146.40±7.35	0.08ns
	5%	187.40±7.07	158.10±55.30	1.42ns
	10%	184.40±13.01	177.00±21.78	0.36ns
	25%	223.10±12.02	200.20±21.92	1.11ns
	50%	243.00±18.81	256.85±9.26	0.67ns
	100%	267.00±28.57	280.60±9.62	0.66ns
	ALT NL U/L	Control	31.70±2.83	40.00±4.10
1%		32.00±3.54	90.30±11.17	7.77**
5%		37.50±1.41	38.50±20.65	0.13ns
10%		21.50±4.53	42.90±6.22	2.85ns
25%		53.10±6.36	29.95±6.01	3.09ns
50%		79.10±3.68	55.20±4.24	3.19*
100%		41.80±4.24	74.40±3.39	4.35**
GLU MMOL		Control	5.20±0.71	5.30±0.42
	1%	5.80±0.57	4.60±0.28	2.37ns
	5%	4.30±0.42	5.30±0.28	1.97ns
	10%	4.70±0.57	4.70±0.99	0.00ns
	25%	5.00±0.42	4.60±0.42	0.79ns
	50%	4.80±0.57	4.20±0.14	1.18ns
	100%	5.60±0.42	5.00±0.28	1.18ns
	ALB b/l	Control	41.10±2.55	19.40±2.69
1%		24.00±3.54	20.70±2.69	0.52ns
5%		35.40±35.98	33.30±6.08	0.33ns
10%		23.10±2.55	34.10±3.82	1.75ns
25%		25.40±8.20	26.00±7.35	0.10ns
50%		35.60±1.56	28.25±5.59	1.17ns
100%		30.00±6.65	31.30±2.97	0.21ns
T.P g/l		Control	73.40±5.66	62.90±6.51
	1%	58.60±4.24	60.00±3.96	0.31ns
	5%	66.90±2.83	65.10±3.82	0.39ns
	10%	48.80±2.55	70.09±6.38	4.63ns
	25%	63.70±0.71	58.80±6.93	1.09ns
	50%	70.10±3.11	70.40±4.10	0.07ns
	100%	62.90±5.66	64.20±3.25	0.28ns
	HDL Mmol/l	Control	1.48±0.11	1.20±0.14
1%		1.00±0.30	1.15±1.15	0.78ns
5%		1.67±0.13	1.19±1.19	2.51ns
10%		1.26±0.37	1.43±1.43	0.89ns
25%		0.85±0.06	1.45±1.45	3.14ns
50%		1.43±0.13	1.36±1.36	0.36ns
100%		1.26±0.21	1.44±1.44	0.94ns
LML Mmol/l		Control	1.88±0.05	2.07±0.16
	1%	1.55±0.06	1.49±0.18	0.35ns
	5%	2.48±0.33	1.68±0.23	4.71**

	10%	1.46±0.17	2.16±0.18	4.12**
	25%	1.61±0.17	1.07±0.17	3.18*
	50%	1.81±0.16	2.23±0.13	2.47ns
	100%	1.89±0.08	0.54±0.10	7.95**
CHOL Mmol/l	Control	2.44±0.25	2.43±0.08	0.03ns
	1%	2.21±0.08	2.06±0.28	0.44ns
	5%	3.13±0.40	2.15±0.23	2.88ns
	10%	1.77±0.07	2.93±0.23	3.41*
	25%	2.19±0.13	3.20±1.02	2.97ns
	50%	2.66±0.25	2.92±0.08	0.77ns
	100%	2.25±0.25	2.38±0.06	0.38ns
T.G Mmol/l	Control	1.26±0.13	0.80±0.21	1.95ns
	1%	1.48±0.14	1.27±0.11	0.89ns
	5%	1.44±0.20	1.05±0.37	1.65ns
	10%	1.13±0.49	1.70±0.33	2.41ns
	25%	1.28±0.18	3.70±0.24	10.24**
	50%	1.34±0.18	1.52±0.16	0.76ns
	100%	0.78±0.12	0.89±0.04	0.47ns
ALPH/L u/l	Control	101.80±16.40	97.20±8.77a	0.39ns
	1%	74.60±3.54	75.70±0.00a	0.09ns
	5%	65.70±4.24	60.90±5.37a	0.41ns
	10%	68.40±5.66	61.70±9.62a	0.57ns
	25%	61.70±4.24	64.20±7.78a	0.21ns
	50%	118.80±4.24	93.00±32.95a	2.21ns
	100%	136.00±8.49	139.20±11.46b	0.27ns
BIL µmol/L	100%	2.40±0.20	2.00±0.20	0.94
	50%	2.20±0.20	2.50±0.10	0.71
	25%	3.70±0.40	2.50±0.20	2.83
	10%	3.20±0.50	3.10±0.60	0.24
	5%	2.50±0.10	3.30±0.40	1.89
	1%	1.90±0.20	2.70±0.10	1.89
	Control	2.80±0.10	1.80±0.30	2.36
CREA µmol/L	100%	22.80±2.90	20.20±0.60	0.72
	50%	27.40±2.40	41.60±3.00	3.96*
	25%	18.00±1.40	13.50±1.60	1.25
	10%	4.10±0.50	22.00±5.20	4.99**
	5%	28.40±1.30	21.80±3.00	1.84
	1%	7.50±0.40	16.80±2.50	2.59
	Control	27.60±4.20	16.90±0.20	2.98
UREA Mmol/L	100%	5.40±0.70	4.40±0.70	0.12
	50%	4.00±0.80	8.90±0.30	0.60
	25%	4.60±0.30	5.30±0.40	2.76
	10%	3.40±0.50	5.00±1.70	0.19
	5%	4.80±0.30	3.80±0.30	0.12
	1%	4.50±0.30	3.10±0.10	0.17
	Control	4.60±0.30	3.70±0.20	0.11

*, ** Significant at $p < 0.05$ and 0.01 , respectively; Values represent mean \pm SEM. AST – Aspartate aminotransferase, ALT – Alanine transaminase, GLU – Glutamine, ALB – Albumin, T.P – Total protein, HDL – High Density Lipoprotein, LML – Low Density Lipoprotein, CHOL – Cholesterol, T.G – Triglycerides, ALPH/A – Alpha-Lipoic Acid, BIL – Bilirubin, CREA – Creatinine, UREA – Urea.

3.5 Sperm motility, Sperm count and Sperm Aberrations in the Rats

There was a concentration dependent significance decrease in the sperm motility ($F = 136.72$; $P < 0.01$) compared to the negative control as seen in Fig. 3a. The treatment effect of control and 1% concentration had no significant difference in sperm motility of mice among themselves. Likewise, the treatment effects of 5% and 10% concentrations of leachates on sperm motility in male mice were not significantly different from one another. However, the treatment effect of 25% on sperm motility had a different effect from the treatment of control, 1%, 5%, 10%, 50% and 100% leachate concentration. Similarly, the treatment effect of 50% on sperm motility was significantly different from the treatment effects of control, 1%, 5%, 10%, 25% and 100% leachate concentration. Sperm motility was greatly reduced in male mice treated with 100% leachate concentration compared to males treated with control, 1%, 5%, 10%, 25% and 50% concentration. Furthermore, sperm motility was at its peak in male mice treated with 1% concentration, which was significantly higher than all the administered leachate concentration.

Figure 3a: Percentage sperm motility of male rats treated with e-waste leachate

There was a concentration dependent significance decrease in the sperm count ($F = 125.25$; $P < 0.01$) compared to the negative control as seen in Fig. 3b. Sperm count was at the lowest in male mice administered with 100% leachate concentration compared to the negative control. Sperm count in mice treated with 100% concentration was significantly

lower than mice treated with control, 1%, 5%, 10%, 25% and 50% concentration ($P < 0.01$). Similarly, mice treated with 25% had higher sperm motility than mice treated with 50% and 100% leachate concentration respectively ($P < 0.01$). Also, mice treated with 50% had higher sperm motility than mice treated with 100% leachate concentration respectively ($P < 0.01$) but lower sperm count when compared with mice in the remaining treatment groups. Mice treated with 1% leachate concentration had the highest sperm count, however, the sperm count was not significantly different from the mice treated with control and 5% concentrations. Although, the sperm count of mice treated with 5% concentration was higher than mice treated with 10%, although, there was no significant difference between the treatments on the sperm count of the mice.

Figure 3b: Percentage sperm count of male rats treated with e-waste leachate

There was a concentration dependent significance increase in the sperm aberrations ($F = 69.33$; $P < 0.01$) compared to the negative control as seen in Fig. 3c. No aberrations were observed in the sperm of the mice treated with the control and 1% leachate concentrations. The sperm aberrations were not significantly different between mice treated with 5% and 10% leachate concentrations. The aberrations were not significantly different between mice treated with 10% and 25% leachate concentrations. The mice treated with 100% concentration had the highest aberrations and was found to be significantly different from the aberrations in mice treated with control, 1%, 5%, 10%, 25% and 50% concentrations. The second-highest aberration was observed in mice treated with 50% concentration.

which was significantly different from the treatments of control, 1%, 5%, 10%, 25% and 100% concentrations.

Figure 3c: Percentage sperm aberrations of male rats treated with e-waste leachate

3.6 Comet Assay and DNA Damage

DNA damage observed include single-strand breaks (SSBs), double-strand breaks (DSBs), DNA cross-links, etc. DNA damage was detected in mouse (* p < 0.0001) with R² value 0.9994. Graph shows significant dose dependent increase in DNA damage between the experimental and the control groups. The olive moment increases in the following order: mouse dosed with 100% of Leachate > mouse dosed with 50% of Leachate > mouse dosed with 25% of Leachate > mouse dosed with 10% of Leachate > mouse dosed with 5% of Leachate > mouse dosed with 1% of Leachate (Fig. 4a). In Fig. 4b, graph shows significant dose dependent increase in DNA damage between the experimental groups and the control groups, no significant increase in DNA between the F group and the control. When both genders were compared, DNA damage was observed in mouse (* p < 0.0001). With male and female groups of mice, graph shows significant dose dependent increase in DNA damage between the experimental groups and the control groups; though no significant increase in DNA damage between the Groups E and F when compared with the control (Figure 4c).

Figure 4a: DNA damage in rats treated with e-waste leachates

Figure 4b: DNA damage induced by e-waste leachates in female mice

Figure 4c: Each group of male and female Swiss albino mice, presented side by side, highlighting the DNA damage induced by e-waste leachate.

4.0 Discussion

The observation that physicochemical parameters across all measurement yielded results above the tolerant level and failed to meet the WHO and the NSDWQ standards, rendering them “not within limits is an indication of their potential toxic effects. This corroborates the works of Migliore *et al.* [19] and Nersesyan *et al.* [20] who concluded in their studies that many physical and chemical factors affect stability of human genome and can contribute to the development of civilization diseases, such as cancer, cardiovascular disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease or neurodegenerative diseases.

Electronic waste leachates pose a great risk to the health of people living close to e-waste dumpsites. E-waste leachates have been identified to possess toxic effects on the liver and kidney of Wister rats and Albino mice (*Mus musculus*), and in humans exposed to the leachates [21, 22]. The clinical signs of toxicity observed in the leachate treated rats further confirm the systemic toxicity of electronic waste leachates. Anorexia (loss of appetite) is one of the common symptoms of liver injury attributed to the exposure of test chemicals and it is consistent with the study of Alimba *et al.* [23]. Hair loss, diarrhea, muscular disorder (muscular stiffness and decreased motor activities), reduced activities, blue discoloration and ungroomed hair were common symptoms observed in central nervous and immune systems dysfunction as a result of toxic leachate exposure in mice [23]. The pH of the leachate obtained from the study site was clearly not within limits and this is in sharp contrast with the study of Alimba *et al.* [23] and Anifowoshe *et al.* [24], wherein the pH of leachates obtained fell within the acceptable range of 6.5 - 8.5. The heavy metals analyzed all had values exceeding expected concentration levels. This was similar to the study of Babatunde and Anabuikwe [25], who reported that concentrations of zinc, nickel, iron, copper, lead, chromium and cadmium in the e-waste leachate surpassed the permissible limits. This could be associated with the formation of free radicals [23]. They could exhibit damaging effects to the kidney through ROS formation. Anifowoshe *et al.* [24] reported that the presence of high concentrations of Zn, Cu and Cd in leachate resulted in single strand break in DNA and induced chromosomal aberration. Furthermore, a comprehensive report by Ankit *et al.*, (2021) [26] identified and highlighted the occurrence of heavy metals as a persistent global issue, affecting different geographical locations. Kuntawee *et al.* [27] documented that the levels of e-waste exposure vary

depending on the substances, concentration, and length of exposure, and the implications of high levels of heavy metals in e-waste are significant as they contribute to environmental pollution and may have an impact on human health. The implications include: the emission of heavy metals as particulate matter into the atmosphere, resulting in air pollution, makes burning of e-waste an unpleasant practice. For example, lead and iron fumes as well as dust have been related to cardiovascular and neurological problems as well as cirrhosis [28]. In addition, Genchi *et al.* [29] reported the inhalation of cadmium particulates with renal malfunction and increased risk of various types of cancer including lung, breast, pancreas.

Result in this study showed concurrent increase in the activity of serum ALT and AST seen in both the males and females. This is supported by the work of Ogunlana *et al.* [30], Arojojoye *et al.* [31] and [22]. Acute hepatocellular injury could be caused by the e-waste leachate constituents and could induce necrosis of the liver cells [32, 33]. Collective elevations occurred in AST and ALT revealed hepatotoxicity, and ruptures of cell membrane or increased permeability leading to leakage of the lysosomal enzymes and ALP into the blood stream [34]. This finding was in accordance with the work of Bakare *et al.* [35], who showed that mice exposed to electronic waste (e-waste) leachate experienced a considerable rise in ALT and AST activity. The increase in serum activities of ALT and AST could be accompanied by severe necrosis, congestion and periportal cellular infiltrations of the liver tissues [36]. The study showed a decrease recorded in the serum albumin level in e-waste leachate treated female mice. However, there was no significance observed in the serum albumin levels of male mice. This is in disagreement with the study of Paliya *et al.* [37], who showed that serum albumin levels were not gender-specific but rather affects both genders. The decrease in albumin levels in female mice may indicate disorders in protein synthesis, metabolism and necrosis as a result of interactions of the complex chemicals, such as heavy metals and other constituents of the E-waste [24]. Decrease in serum albumin may also be due to free radical formation which caused protein damage or protein degradation through oxidative stress induction in rats [38]. This study showed a significant decrease in the total protein concentration in the liver of male albino mice exposed to e-waste leachate. This was in agreement with the study of Balogun *et al.* [39], who reported similar concentration-dependent decrease in serum total protein and albumin in rats exposed to leachates from a MSW dumpsite in southwest Nigeria, and it was concluded that it was responsible for a

decreased liver function. The reduction in protein concentration is indicative of hypoproteinaemia [40]. Hypoproteinaemia can cause swelling, fatty liver, skin degeneration, increase the severity of infections and stunt growth in children [41]. In this study, male mice experienced a 79% increase in cholesterol levels treated with 5% e-waste leachate. This is in accordance with previous studies that have reported elevated CHOL levels in mice treated with e-waste leachate [42,43]. CHOL levels often increase as a result of cellular membrane damage and leakage, apoptosis and necrosis of hepatocytes [21]. The HDL levels were not significantly different either between the males and females treated with e-waste leachate. However, LML levels were elevated in male mice treated with 5% e-waste leachate. The females showed reduced LML levels compared to the negative control. When the male mice LML levels and female mice LML levels were compared, analysis showed that differences existed in effects to the treatment of e-waste leachates. Females had significantly lower LML levels compared to males when exposed to 5%, 25% and 100% e-waste leachate respectively. The combination of high levels of triglycerides, low HDL and high HDL can increase the risk of health problems such as coronary heart disease in humans [44]. This shows that females are more likely at risk to develop health issues when compared to males following exposure to electronic waste since females showed a higher TG level (25% concentration; $P \leq 0.05$), CHOL levels and lower HDL levels significantly different from the males. The significant increase in the activities AST, ALT and LDH, with an insignificant decrease in serum albumin observed in both exposed male and female albino mice indicate cytotoxicity and progressive chronic hepatocellular injury, suggesting that it may have been caused by oxygen deficiency and/or the presence of ROS induced by the metals or other environmental components [23,45].

Serum creatinine (sCr) and serum urea, are insensitive and non-specific markers for early renal damage [46]. Increase in blood urea and creatinine in leachate-treated rats compared to the negative control may be a sign of kidney damage because leachates with Cd, Cr, and as were found to have damaged renal tubular cells and decreased glomerular filtration rate [23,47]. Heavy metals readily bio-accumulate in the kidney and are responsible for a high number of nephrotoxicity observed in mammals [48]. There was a significant increase in the level of creatinine (CREA), bilirubin (BIL) and urea concentration in mice of both genders treated with 50% concentration of electronic waste (e-waste) leachate. The elevation of these biomarkers is usually associated with impairment of renal function.

According to Ogunsuyi *et al.* [49], elevated levels of urea can be caused by impaired kidney and the excessive breakdown of tissue protein caused by wasting diseases. An increased level of creatinine is an indicator of poor kidney failure. In progressive chronic kidney disease (CKD), Kashani *et al.* [50] found that the increase in serum creatinine levels may not correspond proportionally to the decline in glomerular filtration rate (GFR). Sex difference was not a determining factor in respect to biochemical parameters' reaction to leachate treatment. The leachate treatments affected both genders equally except for cases in 10% and 50% treatment on creatinine. However, this does not give a conclusive report on gender playing a role in relation to the effect of leachates [23].

This study showed a steady decrease in the sperm motility of male mice treated with varying leachates concentration. This is in accordance with the study of Adedara *et al.* [51] who showed that sperm motility was decreased significantly at 12.5% and 25% at Olushosun municipal landfill leachate (OMLL) without affecting sperm viability. Similarly, this study is in agreement with the work of Akintunde *et al.* [52] which showed that sperm motility was greatly affected by the treatment of waste from Elewi Odo municipal battery recycling site leachate (EOMBARS), an e-waste leachate obtained from a recycling site. The sperm motility was greatly reduced forming headless tails and bent tails in some of the mice administered with EOMBARS. This present study also showed a dose dependent decrease in sperm count of mice treated with leachates compared to the control. This is in agreement with previously established researches [51,52, 53]. Akintunde *et al.* [52] showed a decrease in sperm count of rats exposed to OMLL, although following withdrawal of OMLL treatment, sperm count was restored to near control. Yakubu and Omar [53] showed that contaminated groundwater samples exposed to e-waste leachate had a negative impact on the sperm count of the rats exposed. The observed abnormalities imply that the e-waste leachate has genotoxic effect on the sperm cells which might occur during the early stages of spermatogenesis. Our result is in line with the result of previous studies [52, 24, 53]. It is possible that the toxic metals and metalloids and other substances in the leachate interfered with the integrity of spermatogonia chromosomes and or expression of genes that stabilize the fidelity of DNA during spermatogenesis as earlier stated by Yahaya *et al.* [54]. In comet assay, the high R2 values reported suggest a strong correlation between leachate concentration and DNA damage in mice. The interpretation of the olive moment increasing in a particular order provides a

visual representation of the dose-response relationship between leachate and DNA damage in mice. Overall, the findings suggest that there is a significant increase in DNA damage in mice exposed to leachate, with no significant differences between the male and female groups.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

This study showed the genetic toxicity of both somatic and germ cells in mice exposed to soil leachate from e-waste, and the negative effects are evidence of soil contamination by heavy metals as a result of informal open dumpsites for e-waste. These non-specific reported toxicities, which can be categorized as genotoxic properties shown by the somatic cells of the animal model used, are caused by the high concentrations of organic and heavy metal pollutants in the leachate. Also, the findings of this study show that long term exposure to e-waste, whether occupationally or non-occupationally, is associated with an increased risk of DNA damage, as determined by the DNA damage biomarker, the comet assay as well as other health diseases. However, it is likely that the consequences of DNA damage for the future fate of a cell depends on its genomic composition, for example, mutations in DNA-damage-repair related genes. Future research should include additional DNA abnormalities, such as epigenetic indicators like DNA methylation, post-translational histone modifications, and RNA frequencies, to better understand the mechanisms of the health effects induced by e-waste. Therefore, it is highly recommended that minimizing human exposure to e-waste is essential to prevent adverse health effects. Proper management and disposal of e-waste are crucial to mitigate its toxic effects on human health and the environment.

6.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors report that there are no competing interests to declare.

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